

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SLEEP DISORDERS DEVELOPED AS POST-COVID SYNDROME.

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Introduction: The post-COVID period has been affecting the population of Uzbekistan, with outcomes registering every one-third of patients who have visited Mental Health Centers in the country until today. Between 2021 and 2023, the prevalence of sleep disorders as a post-COVID syndrome increased from 26.4% to 43.8% among those who sought assistance at the Psychiatric and Mental Health Center. This substantial increase is a significant indicator and warrants an examination of the proliferation level of unregistered post-COVID syndromes, especially sleep deprivation, among the population, and the development of a special psychotherapy program based on these findings.

Methods: Data were collected from 200 patients treated for COVID-19 and observed for post COVID syndromes, including registered sleep disorders, at the Psychiatric and Mental Health Center between 2021 and 2023. Of the 200 patients, 110 were female and 90 were male. All individuals in the cohort were assessed for the clinical structure of sleep disorders using a specialized questionnaire addressing medical and psychological status.

Results: The current investigation showed that the prevalence of sleep disorders during the research years reached 43.8% of the total number of all post-COVID syndromes, including insomnia (42.7%), obstructive sleep apnea (9.7%), hypersomnia (32.5%), narcolepsy (7.6%), and restless leg syndrome (15.9%). Additionally, other neuropsychiatric conditions, including cognitive dysfunction, anxiety, panic disorders, depression, somatic symptom disorders, and partial memory loss, collectively reached 24.7%. The manifestation of these symptoms in one patient has a serious impact on their lifestyle and undermines social adaptation.

Conclusion: A comparative analysis of sleep disorders in the studied groups revealed an increased risk of developing insomnia. Due to the complexity of gathering all patients with post COVID syndromes at Mental Health clinics, the rate of COVID-19-related sleep disorders remains high in Uzbekistan. This issue will not be resolved until a specialized medical psychological questionnaire is employed among the population who have not yet been registered and treated with assistance in special psychotherapy methods.

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